

THE ROLE OF PUBLIC ASSOCIATIONS AND FAMILY COOPERATION IN SHAPING THE SPIRITUALITY OF YOUTH

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In today's rapidly changing era of globalization, Uzbekistan considers its future and prospects to be directly connected with the development and preservation of the family. This is clearly reflected in the fact that building a modern, exemplary and prosperous family, while enriching our traditional values, has become one of the priority directions of state policy.

It is well known that family well-being, as a part of social policy, is given special attention in our society and is being elevated to the level of state policy. Therefore, it is necessary to widely establish cooperation between public associations and the family in shaping the spirituality of youth. According to the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the state guarantees the rights and legal interests of public associations and ensures equal opportunities for them to participate in social life.

The future of society and the strength of the state are directly connected with the family. In shaping the spirituality of youth, it is important to work in close cooperation with families. The First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan I.A. Karimov emphasized in his book "High Spirituality – An Invincible Force":

"The most important task ahead of us today is to place the meaning and essence of such noble concepts as the perfect individual, social cooperation, interethnic harmony, and interfaith tolerance – which form an integral part of our national idea – at the center of our spiritual, educational, and upbringing activities, to raise them to a new stage, and to educate our young generation as mature people with an independent worldview."

From our rich scientific and cultural heritage, ancient traditions and customs, it is evident that the family has always been considered a sacred value in any time and place. The stronger the family, which is based on educational, spiritual-enlightenment, moral, and socio-legal relations, the more stable the society will be. Our ancestors understood this very well.

It is well known that the upbringing of children in the family is of great importance. Therefore, parents always paid special attention to the education and upbringing of their children. Parents with high intellectual and moral potential became a source of pride for their children and influenced their worldview. At all times and in all places, the upbringing of children has been considered a key value.

In families vulnerable to social threats, pedagogical preventive opportunities in combating social dangers - such as responding to thought with thought, to idea with idea, and to ignorance with enlightenment - play an important role. The significance of the older generation's role, experience, methods, forms, and means in youth education was explained by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoyev through the words of Abdurauf Fitrat:

"A nation's striving towards a clear goal, its prosperity, honor, and dignity, its rise to greatness or its decline into weakness and humiliation, bearing the burden of misfortune, being forgotten and enslaved by others - all of this depends on the upbringing received from parents in childhood."

To strengthen cooperation between family, neighborhood (mahalla), and educational institutions, it is important to hold public discussions on education-related issues at our institute, to define necessary measures, to enhance cooperation between law enforcement bodies and local

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citizens' assemblies, and to further develop spiritual-enlightenment and educational collaboration aimed at improving the system of protecting youth rights.